

Efficacy Of Superabsorbent Polymer On Soil Moisture And Growth Of Lakatan Banana (*Musa Sapientum* L.) Under Nursery Condition

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Abstract: The study was carried out to evaluate the efficacy of superabsorbent polymer on growth and quality of lakatan banana under nursery condition at the Research Experimental Area, Campus Research Department, Isabela State University, Echague, Isabela. Five different concentrations of superabsorbent polymer were used ($T_1=0$ grams or control, $T_2=2.0$ grams, $T_3=4.0$ grams, $T_4=6.0$ grams and $T_5=8.0$ grams, each mixed with the prepared soil media) and set as treatments. Data analysis was done using the Analysis of Variance for Completely Randomized Design. Results showed that using superabsorbent polymer led to a significant increase on plant height at 14 DAT ($p<0.05$), 28 DAT ($p<0.01$), 42 DAT ($p<0.01$) and 56 DAT ($p<0.05$). Result also showed that application of superabsorbent polymer has a positive effect on the pseudostem girth at 14 DAT ($p<0.01$) and leaf area at 70 DAT ($p<0.05$) of lakatan banana. This study also proves that amendments of superabsorbent polymer on the soil improved the soil physical properties, reduced soil erosion and nutrient loss and required significantly less quantity of water and least frequency of watering as compared to control.

Index Terms: Banana, Efficacy, Growth Parameters, Lakatan, Nursery Condition, Soil moisture content, Superabsorbent Polymer

1. INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, banana emerges as the most important fruit crop especially in rural areas. It is used to substitute staple food such as rice and corn because of its high nutritional value. Aside from food, banana also serves as sources of livelihood on small scale farmers in rural areas. Data from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nation shows that the production of banana in the country has decreased from 2010 to 2013. Data also shows that the occurrence of drought is one of the reasons for the decrease of banana production. Drought severely affects banana plant by restricting not only the growth but also the productivity of the crop [1]. Like any other crops, bananas also requires adequate amount of water to grow and to increase crop yields [4]. One of the ways to increase the water supply in soil is applying super absorbent polymers that supply water for crop roots [6]. Super Absorbent Polymers or SAPs are networks of polymer chains and highly absorbent to water molecules [7]. SAPs have great potential in soil restoration and in storing readily available water for the plant [8]. Adding SAPs on soil can also improve soil characteristics such as soil water holding capacity, decrease evapotranspiration and allow plants to mitigate the drought stress [5]. This study, therefore, was designed to investigate the performance of lakatan banana and soil moisture applied with super absorbent polymers under nursery conditions. Specifically it aimed to determine the efficacy of the different rates of application of superabsorbent polymers on soil moisture, growth and development of lakatan banana, and determine which treatment combinations will give the best results.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

This study was conducted at the Research Department, Isabela State University, Echague, Isabela. The type of climate in the study area is tropical where the average annual temperature is 26.8 °C. The warmest month of the year is during the month of May with the average temperature of 29.0 °C while the lowest average temperature of the year observed during the month of January with an average temperature of 24.0 °C. Annual precipitation in the study area averages 1,903

mm. The month of February is driest month in the study area with an average rainfall amount of 46 mm, while most precipitation falls during the month of November with an average rainfall amount of 281 mm [2].

2.2 Procedures in Nursery

The mixture of garden soil and carbonized rice hull (1:1 ratio) was used as the soil media. The polyethylene bags measuring 6 inches width and 7 inches high were filled up with the mixture of superabsorbent polymer or hydrophilic polymers and prepared soil media. For this study, 60 meriplants with an average height of 4 inches were used and obtained at the Isabela State University Tissue Culture Laboratory, Echague, Isabela. The meriplants were planted in individual pots and done in partially shaded area. Regular weeding was done. Water application interval was 2-3 days. Spraying of Insecticides and fungicides were also done as often as necessary to prevent the occurrence of pest and insect.

2.3 Data Gathering

Growth parameters of Lakatan banana such as Plant Height, Pseudostem Girth and Leaf Area were gathered from the experiment and were measured using the Vernier Caliper. Soil moisture content was also determined using Real-time sensor (Digital Moisture Meter).

2.4 Experimental Design and Treatments

The data was analyzed following the Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The software Statistical tool for Agricultural Research (STAR) was used in the analysis. Significant results of treatments were compared using LSD.

Treatments: Levels of Application

$T_1 = 0$ gram (Control)

$T_2 = 2$ grams

$T_3 = 4$ grams

$T_4 = 6$ grams

$T_5 = 8$ grams

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Plant Height

One of the most important morphological parameters related

to growth and development of the crop is the plant height. Growth involves both cell growth and development. Results indicate that rate of superabsorbent polymer had a very high significant influence on plant height at 14 DAT ($P \leq 0.05$), 28 DAT ($P \leq 0.01$), 42 DAT ($P \leq 0.01$) and 56 DAT ($P \leq 0.05$), as shown in table 1. However, application of superabsorbent polymer at 70 DAT has no significant effect on plant height. Results also showed that no application of superabsorbent polymer resulted in a considerable reduction in plant height. This implies that adding superabsorbent polymer concentration on the soil has a positive effect on the growth of banana particularly on height. This increased can be attributed to the water availability and indirectly nutrients on the plants that resulted an increase on the activity of cell division, cell expansion and elongation that ultimately leading to an increased on banana plant height.

Table 1. Plant Height of banana using SAPs

Treatments	Plant height (cm)				
	Days after transplanting (DAT)				
	14	28	42	56	70
0 grams	3.30 ^b	7.00 ^c	8.87 ^c	14.23 ^c	16.29
2 grams	4.30 ^a	8.40 ^b	11.47 ^{ab}	19.43 ^a	21.61
4 grams	4.77 ^a	9.83 ^a	12.43 ^a	18.87 ^{ab}	20.43
6 grams	4.29 ^a	7.43 ^c	10.60 ^b	18.10 ^{ab}	22.80
8 grams	4.87 ^a	8.63 ^b	11.57 ^{ab}	17.17 ^b	21.77
CV (%)	11.86	6.63	7.39	8.47	8.17
F-Test	*	**	**	*	ns

3.2 Pseudostem girth

As for the pseudostem girth of the lakatan banana, high significant effect was observed only on the plant at 14 DAT ($P \leq 0.01$), while no significant effect was observed on 28 DAT, 42 DAT, 56 DAT and 70 DAT as shown in table 2. The largest size of the pseudostem girth at 14 DAT was noticed with the rates of 6 grams of superabsorbent polymers (0.30 cm) while the smallest size of the pseudostem girth (0.19 cm) was shown with the plants untreated with the superabsorbent polymers. Result also shows that, application of superabsorbent polymer has a positive effect on the plant growth parameters particularly on the pseudostem girth of banana. The increase in size of the pseudostem girth of banana might be attributed to the characteristics of the superabsorbent polymer to retain and store large amount of water and nutrients as required by the plant to improve growth and development.

Table 2. Pseudostem of banana using superabsorbent polymers, (cm)

Treatments	Pseudostem Girth (cm)				
	Days after transplanting (DAT)				
	14	28	42	56	70
0 grams	0.19 ^c	0.22	1.16	1.23	1.51
2 grams	0.23 ^b	0.28	1.21	1.34	1.56
4 grams	0.21 ^b	0.27	1.25	1.85	1.69
6 grams	0.30 ^a	0.32	1.23	1.39	1.58
8 grams	0.23 ^b	0.31	1.2	1.33	1.55
CV (%)	75.31	12.88	16.53	28.83	21.92
F-Test	**	ns	ns	ns	ns

3.3 Leaf Area (LA)

The leaf area (LA) greatly affects the photosynthetic capacity of the plant. However, the decrease in leaf area is an early response to water deficit. In this study, the superabsorbent

polymers or SAP significantly affect the LA of lakatan banana at 70 DAP ($P \leq 0.05$) as shown in Table 3. However, no significant effect was observed on the leaf area at 14, 28, 42 and 56 days after transplanting. The total leaf area at 70 DAT showed significant variation at various rates of superabsorbent polymers whereby biggest total leaf area were produced by the plants applied with different rates of superabsorbent polymers with means ranging from 1512.59 cm to 1724.78 cm. The least total leaf area was observed in control or no superabsorbent polymer application with a mean of 1033.49 cm. The result of the study also shows that application of superabsorbent polymers significantly increased the leaf area of the plant. This implies that the superabsorbent polymers increase the turgor pressure inside the cells by giving the plants plenty amount of water which resulted increase on the leaf area.

Table 3. Leaf Area of banana using superabsorbent polymers

Treatments	Leaf Area (cm ²)				
	Days after transplanting (DAT)				
	14	28	42	56	70
0 grams	24.23	32.20	545.17	680.55	1033.49 ^b
2 grams	29.11	67.92	676.53	984.95	1647.57 ^a
4 grams	21.91	41.76	782.27	1067.57	1724.78 ^a
6 grams	31.43	56.77	759.58	1005.10	1556.68 ^a
8 grams	25.28	57.70	710.83	948.00	1512.59 ^a
CV (%)	23.42	28.85	16.27	14.45	14.68
F-Test	ns	ns	ns	ns	*

3.4 Soil Moisture

The use of superabsorbent polymer in soils improves both the nutritional and water status of plants. Result shows that that addition of superabsorbent polymer to the soil matrix increased the water holding capacity as well as water available to plants. The superabsorbent polymer also prolonged water availability for plant use when irrigation stopped as shown in fig. 1.

Fig.1. Effects of superabsorbent polymer on soil moisture

4 CONCLUSION

The result of the study proved that the utilization of superabsorbent polymer has a positive impact on the growth and development of lakatan banana. As a result, applying different rates of superabsorbent polymer on plants produced tallest plant height, increase pseudostem girth size, produced large leaf area and retain more soil moisture for plant

compared to plants without superabsorbent polymer application. This study also shows that amendments of superabsorbent polymer on the soil improve the soil physical properties, reduce soil erosion and nutrient loss and require significantly less quantity of water and least frequency of watering as compared to control.

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